

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3233432

УДК : 325.14

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FEATURES OF REGULATION OF THE MIGRATION PROCESSES IN THE EUROPEAN UNION COUNTRIES

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ МІГРАЦІЙНИХ ПРОЦЕСІВ У КРАЇНАХ ЄВРОПЕЙСЬКОГО СОЮЗУ

The features of the migration situation in the countries of the European Union are analyzed. Studied the policy trends of the European Union countries regarding migrants. The main forms of the migration movement and the factors influencing the growth of migration flows in the modern world are highlighted. The influence of migration processes on the labor market and social attitudes in the recipient countries has been revealed.

Keywords: *migration policy, migration processes, forms of migration, labor market, migration factors.*

Проаналізовано особливості міграційної ситуації в країнах Європейського Союзу. Досліджено тенденції політики країн Європейського Союзу відносно мігрантів. Висвітлено основні форми міграційного руху та фактори, що впливають на зростання міграційних потоків у сучасному світі. Виявлено вплив міграційних процесів на ринок праці та соціальні настрої у країнах-реципієнтах.

Ключові слова: *міграційна політика, міграційні процеси, форми міграції, ринок праці, фактори міграції.*

Problem setting. In the modern world in recent decades, the problems of external migration processes have become extremely topical, and a number of circumstances indicate that in the near future they will not lose their significance. The consequences of migration are manifested in political, social, economic, cultural, psychological and other areas.

Among the most significant consequences of migration are changes in the situation on the labor market, conflicts in the places of compact settlement of

migrants, the impact of migration on the ethnic and social structure of the population. In one form or another, on one scale or another, migration flows affect all European countries and their management, and therefore giving them civilized forms becomes the most important requirement of international politics and economics. This is especially important in the context of ongoing conflicts in the Middle East, as well as in connection with the difficult economic situation in the countries of the former USSR.

Recent research and publication analysis. Many Ukrainian and foreign scientists paid attention to the problems of studying the migration processes at different times. Among them there are such academic figures as O. A. Malinovskaya, O. V. Poznyak, E. S. Maltseva, N. A. Pack, C. Van Mol, J. Estevens, M. Baldwin-Edwards and others.

At the same time, the transience of what is happening in the modern world requires constant research based on the ongoing changes in the economic, political and social spheres of both receiving countries and countries with high outgoing migration flows.

Paper objective. The purpose of this article is to study the migration processes that occur in the countries of the European Union, as well as to identify the features of their regulatory system in these countries.

Paper main body. Migration processes in the EU countries are shaped by the influence and influence of many factors, circumstances, situations. These are the demographic development of the country, the personal and family circumstances of citizens, the material and cultural standard of living of the population, the socio-political situation in the country, the economic situation, the situation in the labor market, public safety, the activities of large transnational corporations and much more. There are different criteria according to which certain types and forms of migration qualify: depending on the duration - temporary, long-term or permanent migration: depending on geographical factors - regional, border, pendulum, transit: depending on administrative and legal regulation - voluntary, legal, illegal, expulsion, deportation, relocation, re-emigration.

Recently, the tendency to erase the obvious differences between individual forms of migration, sometimes difficult to determine their real motives and character, is becoming more and more evident. There is a kind of interpenetration of different forms of migration, the boundaries between them become less clear, blurred. For example, a seasonal departure for work may turn into a long-term migration, illegal emigration may become legal after obtaining the appropriate permission to stay in the country. All these moments are to some extent inherent in all European countries.

In the modern world, the right to relocate - with the ability to legally leave his country - is almost universally recognized as one of the fundamental human rights. In this case, it is not only about the humanistic and political sense of this formula as its main principle, but also about its economic aspects. The freedom of movement of people is considered on a par with the free movement of goods,

services, capital. The economic reasons for migration include overpopulation, a large demographic increase, especially in conditions of a shortage of jobs, high unemployment; crisis economic situation in the country, long-term economic depression, low living standards of the population; significant distortions in the gender and age structure of the population, the lack of life prospects for young people who have reached working age: the lack of opportunities for the development of science and culture, military actions on the territory of states [1].

Western European countries began to take steps to establish control over migration processes and limit the flow of new immigrants. The reasons for the need for significant changes in the immigration policy of the European Union countries should include an excess of labor in the European labor market, which led to social tensions, anti-immigrant sentiment, and, as a result, extremist manifestations and racial persecution.

Currently, migration policy in the EU countries is formed under the influence of two determining factors:

- considered in the recent past as a “temporary phenomenon” migrant labor has acquired the status of one of the important components that have an impact on the economy, regardless of the state of the economic situation in the importing countries;

- there is a constant increase in the average length of stay of migrants in a country that accepts labor. The migrant is becoming increasingly long-term resident of the importing country, which changes the very nature of interstate migration. At the same time, there are significant changes in the migration policy of Western European countries in relation to non-EU countries [3].

The immigration policy of the countries of the European Union, despite some differences and national peculiarities, is currently characterized by the following principles: implementation of a policy for restricting the entry of low-skilled labor force into the country: combating illegal immigration: carrying out a policy of re-emigration [4].

The growth of labor migration is a kind of transfer and, in the context of the internationalization of economic processes, it can become a motor for economic growth and welfare for the region as a whole. EU expansion will entail economic changes, because the increase in population by 20% will occur simultaneously with an increase in GDP of only 5%, and the gap between the richest and poorest regions (in terms of GDP per capita) within the union will increase from fivefold to ninefold. In view of the foregoing, immigration is an indispensable means for overcoming the socioeconomic and fiscal implications of a reduction in the size of the army of labor in the countries of the “old” Europe [2].

The reasons affecting international labor migration are determined by two main parameters: the gap in income levels and unemployment. The Polish experience and data on migration (of relatively small scale) after joining the EU suggests that the level of outflow of labor is affected by improved lives in the countries of exit, especially in the long run. But there is another factor explaining the

reasons for migration to the west - this is a fairly high demand for foreign labor, despite the difficult situation in the local labor markets. Moreover, the demand extends to three main categories of workers: unskilled workers in the agricultural and services sectors, people with average qualifications in the health and social sectors, and highly qualified personnel in knowledge-intensive areas of the economy [5].

Countries with a “surplus of people with higher education”, to which the new members of the European Community from CEE belong, can only benefit from the fact that their specialists gain professional and life experience abroad. According to the calculations of the European Commission, 350 thousand migrants from the “new” states of the European Union will come annually to live in “old” Europe. The entry of new countries into the EU will only increase the flow of immigrants from Eastern Europe for the first time. Further improvement of living conditions in these countries will reduce the number of people willing to live and work in the West. A number of studies suggest that the introduction of a free labor movement regime may result in the migration of about 5% of the population of new countries to the territory of “old” Europe.

Conclusions of the research. Migration increases the financial burden in the countries - sources of migration, because the population there will grow at the same pace as in Western Europe, while the birth rate has sharply decreased since the beginning of the transition period. And if, most often, a migrant receiving high qualifications and education, including higher education, was paid from the state treasury, the consequences for the budget of the countries of the region would be negative, and for the host country - positive. Improving the allocation of human resources could be facilitated by the development of a mechanism to compensate for these costs to the specialist’s country of origin. The political and military factors remain the main cause of forced migration. Its relationship with economic and social causes has become closer. Together they initiate and support migratory attitudes.

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